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Ifqar: Signs of Involvement in Economic Warfare from Individual Perspective

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Abstract

Economic warfare is traditionally associated with poverty, but a more nuanced understanding reveals it as a deliberate effort to impoverish individuals or groups, a process termed *Ifqar* (to make poor). Unlike general poverty, economic warfare involves coercion or force, where individuals are systematically deprived of economic opportunities and resources. This article explores the nature and mechanisms of economic warfare, including forced unemployment, denial of capital, and artificially enhancing competitors through fraud or nepotism. External actors such as employers, competitors, and institutions play key roles in sabotaging individuals' economic stability. These tactics not only lead to financial hardship but also exert severe psychological pressure on victims, who struggle to maintain ethical values in hostile environments. The broader societal impact includes diminished economic power and reduced access to resources, which further weakens communities. Economic warfare, characterized by deliberate coercion, poses significant challenges to individuals and society, requiring a deep understanding to foster fairer economic policies.

Keywords: Ifqar, Economic warfare

Introduction

Economic warfare is often associated with poverty from a general perspective, but from a more nuanced viewpoint, it can be described as a deliberate effort to impoverish individuals or groups, a process known as *Ifqar* (from the Arabic term meaning "to make poor"). The term *Ifqar* is the antithesis of *afkhar* (to enrich or exalt), and it occurs when a person is forcibly dragged down from their position of stability or prosperity. In this context, the presence of coercion or force is essential to define the situation as economic warfare. Mere poverty, absent of forceful actions, cannot be perceived as a battleground in this context.

This article aims to explore the nature of economic warfare, the mechanisms through which it unfolds, and the impact it has on individuals and society at large. By analyzing the signs and tactics used in such conflicts, we can better understand how economic warfare operates both on an individual and systemic level.

Defining Economic Warfare

Forced Impoverishment (*Ifqar*)

The essence of economic warfare lies in the forced impoverishment of individuals, often carried out through mechanisms designed to prevent access to economic opportunities or resources. Examples include:

1. **Unemployment despite capability:** One hallmark of economic warfare is deliberately keeping competent individuals out of employment, even when they possess the necessary skills and qualifications. This tactic strips them of their means of livelihood and can force them into a state of financial insecurity.
2. **Lack of investment for capable individuals:** Another sign of economic warfare is the inability to secure capital to start or continue a business despite having the requisite experience and expertise. This is not due to a lack of potential but rather an intentional blockade to prevent economic progression.

3. **Artificially enhanced competitors:** The creation of false or inflated capabilities among competitors through fraud, favoritism, or manipulation of systems is another weapon in economic warfare. By creating fake merit or manipulating processes, undeserving individuals or entities are placed in favorable positions, sidelining those who truly adhere to standards and ethics.

These strategies represent a systematic effort to undermine individuals and groups, pulling them into economic battlegrounds where the odds are stacked against them.

Mechanisms of Economic Warfare

The Role of Employers, Rivals, and Institutions

Economic warfare does not necessarily begin with the affected individual. Instead, it is often initiated by external actors such as employers, rivals, banks, governments, or even hostile foreign states. These actors can engage in tactics that sabotage the economic well-being of individuals or groups, intentionally creating hardships. For example, employers may deliberately dismiss highly qualified employees (PhDs, postdoctoral researchers, etc.) to prevent them from completing specialized projects due to a lack of funding or resources. This not only hinders their professional growth but also pushes them into economic instability.

Rivals also play a significant role in economic warfare. By falsifying qualifications and inflating their résumés with worthless achievements, they can secure positions that rightfully belong to those who adhere to ethical standards. This undermines the integrity of merit-based employment and research, pushing capable individuals into a battle for survival in an unfair competitive environment.

Nepotism and Favoritism

Another aspect of economic warfare is nepotism or favoritism in hiring practices, which further exacerbates economic inequality. In many cases, competent individuals are excluded from opportunities due to preferential treatment given to less qualified individuals with personal or political connections. This, in turn, forces those with genuine talent and expertise into a disadvantaged economic position, further fueling their struggles.

Nepotism can distort labor markets and perpetuate cycles of poverty and inequality, making it one of the more insidious tools of economic warfare. Those who rely on honesty, integrity, and hard work may find themselves systematically excluded from opportunities, thereby pushing them further into economic marginalization.

The Psychological Toll of Economic Warfare

Economic warfare does not only manifest in material deprivation. It also imposes severe psychological pressure on its victims, who may find themselves constantly at odds with a system that seems designed to work against them. The constant effort to maintain ethical standards, such as absolute honesty, diligence, and morality, often proves detrimental in an environment where these traits are not rewarded. This "war on values" can be just as damaging as the financial hardships imposed by economic warfare, leading individuals to question the fairness of the system and their place within it.

Systemic Impacts on Society

Economic warfare also has broader societal implications. It can lead to the overall degradation of a community's economic power, particularly when large segments of the population are unable to access employment, capital, or other resources necessary for financial stability. This reduces the overall purchasing power of society and negatively impacts the quality of life for all. The decline in income, reduced access to housing, and limited opportunities for recreation and food security are symptoms of an economically weakened society.

However, for individuals caught in the direct line of economic warfare, the burden is even heavier. In these cases, the element of "coercion" is even more pronounced, as they are often systematically targeted through overt or covert means to ensure their economic disenfranchisement.

Conclusion

Economic warfare is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon, with far-reaching consequences for individuals and society at large. The strategies used in such warfare, from deliberate unemployment to artificial enhancement of competitors, aim to impoverish individuals and exclude them from economic participation. By examining the

mechanisms behind these actions, it becomes evident that economic warfare is not simply a byproduct of natural market forces but rather a targeted and deliberate strategy designed to maintain control and dominance over resources and opportunities.

To address the challenges posed by economic warfare, it is essential to recognize its signs and understand the systemic and individual impacts. Only then can society begin to implement policies and practices that foster economic fairness and prevent the continued marginalization of capable individuals.

References

1. Galtung, J. (1984). *The Struggle for Peace: Essays in Peace Research*. Oslo: PRIO.
2. Harvey, D. (2005). *A Brief History of Neoliberalism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
3. Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. New York: Knopf.
4. Piketty, T. (2014). *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
5. Krugman, P. (2009). *The Return of Depression Economics and the Crisis of 2008*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company.